

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE

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In the collection of materials of the conference, the role and role of Science, Education and production in the era of globalization, the pressing problems of the issues of interaction of these processes, feedback on their solutions were presented by mature specialists of the field.

In addition, research on the scientific and practical topic, carried out in the economics, Exact Sciences, Natural Sciences and socio-humanities during the globalization period, information is presented in the scientific and practical fields, which includes the latest innovative technologies in the fields of production.

It can be argued that this collection is one of the specific intersections of current thoughts and innovative ideas of the world of science. This scientific and practical conference was actively attended by professors and scientific researchers engaged in scientific research in Uzbekistan and foreign countries. In increasing the position of the scientific and practical conference, the professors and teachers of domestic and foreign higher educational institutions made a significant contribution.

Professors and teachers of foreign higher educational institutions who actively participated in the work of the conference made a worthy contribution to the high level of interaction with scientists of our country. The processes of international cooperation with foreign countries and exchange with them in the field of Science in the era of globalization have a positive effect on the development of Higher Education, the fields of Science and production. The materials of this conference are special in that they include a wide range of research, from theoretical developments to practical solutions, demonstrating the diversity of approaches and directions in this area.

In conclusion, it should be noted that this scientific and practical conference will be a very useful collection for everyone who is interested in modern research in the fields of further development of Higher Education, Science, Education and production in the era of globalization. The authors are responsible for the content and quality of the articles and abstracts included in the collection.

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PARKINSON KASALLIGINING MOLEKULAR MEXANIZMLARI

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Annotatsiya: Parkinson kasalligi markaziy asab tizimining degenerativ kasalliklaridan biri bo‘lib, dopamin neyronlarining progressiv yo‘qolishi bilan xarakterlanadi. Parkinson kasalligi rivojlanishida genetika va atrof-muhit omillari muhim rol o‘ynaydi. Ushbu kasallikni davolashda hozirgi kunda dopaminergik terapiya asosiy usul sifatida qo‘llaniladi. Shuningdek, neyroprotektiv dorilar va gen terapiya kabi yangi yondashuvlar ham rivojlanmoqda. Kelajakda molekulyar mexanizmlarni chuqur o‘rganish orqali shaxsiylashtirilgan terapiya va kasallikni kechiktirish yoki to‘xtatish yo‘llari ishlab chiqilishi mumkin.

Kalit so‘zlar: Parkinson kasalligi, dofamin, noradrenalin, neyrotoksinlar, alfa sinuklein, parkin, yallig‘lanish, mikroglia, sitokinlar, neyrotrafinlar, apoptoz, avtofagiya.

Parkinson kasalligi dofamin darajasining pasayishi bilan xarakterlanadi. Bundan tashqari, Parkinson kasalligi bilan og‘rigan bemorlarning yarmi frontostriatal vositachilik bilan bog‘liq ijro etuvchi disfunktsiyasini, shu jumladan diqqatning yetishmasligi, qisqa muddatli xotira, aqliy ishlov berish tezligi va impulsivlikni ko‘rsatadi. Parkinson kasalligi uchun eng ko‘p qo‘llaniladigan davolash usullari faqat qisman yoki vaqtinchalik samarali bo‘ladi va bemorlarning ozchiligi uchun mavjud yoki qo‘llanilishi mumkin. Ushbu terapiya yo‘qolgan yoki degeneratsiyalangan dopaminergik neyronlarni tiklamaydi, kasallikning rivojlanishini oldini olmaydi yoki kechiktirmaydi, shuning uchun samaraliroq terapevtik vositalarga ehtiyoj juda muhimdir [1].

Aksariyat parkinson kasalligi tarixsiz sporatik (Spd) bo‘ladi. SPD KA neyronlarga nisbatan neyrotoksik bo‘lgan ba‘zi neyrotoksik ekzogen yoki endogen moddalar tufayli yuzaga keladi, bu esa neyronlarning dasturlashtirilgan hujayra o‘limiga (apoptoz yoki autofagiya) olib keladi.

Alfa sinuklein va *parkin* kabi noyob oilaviy parkinson kasalligining (fPD) holatlarining qo‘zg‘atuvchi genlari bo‘yicha so‘nggi tadqiqotlar shuni ko‘rsatadi, ubiquitin protezoma tizimining disfunktsiyasi va natijada noto‘g‘ri qatlamlangan oqsillarni to‘planishiva endoplazmatik retikulum stress neyronlarning o‘limiga olib kelishi mumkin [2].

Keng miqyosli genom bo‘yicha assotsiatsiya tadqiqotlari Parkinson kasalligi bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan 90 tagacha genomik joyni aniqladi. Shu bilan birga aniqlangan genetik xavf omillari kasallikning sezuvchanligi bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan murakkab genetik moyillik bilan bog‘liq bo‘lgan oilaviy kasalliklarning faqat 30% va sporadik parkinson kasallik holatlarining 3% dan 5% gacha tushintiradi. Kodlanmagan

hududlarda joylashgan kasallik xavfi variantlari transkripsiya faktorining bog'lanishini buzishi va sis-regulyatsiya faolligining buzilishiga olib kelishi mumkin. Sis-regulyatsiya elementlaridagi (cRE) buzilishlar kasallikka xos gen ekspressiyasini o'z ichiga olishi va ko'plab kodlanmagan genetik variandlar bilan birgalikda joylashishi Parkinson kasalligi bilan bog'liq epigenomni chuqur o'rganish uchun asos bo'lib xizmat qiladi. Parkinson kasalligida sis-regulyatsiya elementlarni tizimli tekshirish kam bo'lsada, prefrontal korteksda atsetillagan giston H3 lizin 27 landshaftining global disregulyatsiyasi va tartibga solinmagan cRElarga proksimal parkinson kasalligi genom bo'yicha assotsiatsiya tadqiqotlari genlarining lokalizatsiyasi haqida xabar berilgan. Bundan tashqari bitta yadroli ketma-ketlik yondashuvining paydo bo'lishi individual miya hujayralari turlari bo'yicha epigenom landshaftini o'rganishga imkon beradi [3].

Parkinson kasalligi etiologiyasi ko'p yillik tadqiqotlarga qaramay noaniqlik qolmoqda. Parkinson kasalligi holatlarining taxminan 5-10% monogenik shakllar bilan ifodalanadi, ular asosan yosh odamlarda namoyon bo'ladi, kasallikning aksariyat holatlari sporadik va multifaktorial xususiyatga ega. Parkinson kasalligida neyrodegeneratsiya rivojlanishining asosiy molekulyar hodisasi a-sinuklein pufakchali oqsilining konformatsiyasining buzilishi bo'lib, uning neyrotoksik sitoplazmatik agregatlari va Lyui tanachalari neyritlari hosil bo'lishi bilan fibrilizatsiyasini boshlaydi. Parkinson kasalligida a-sinukleinning patologiyasi atrof-muhit omillari, genomik xususiyatlar va tizimli metabolizmning o'ziga xos o'zaro ta'siridan kelib chiqadi, ular birgalikda hujayralarni zararsizlantirish jarayonlarining tabiatini, mitoxondriyalarning ishlashini, sinaptik uzatishni va endosomal transportni belgilaydi. Ko'rib chiqishda parkinson kasalligidagi patologik jarayonning mumkin bo'lgan ekzogen va endogen ko'rinishlari ko'rsatilgan. Etiologik omillarni tahlil qilishda turli neyrotoksinlarning rolga, mitofagiya buzilishiga, Parkinson kasalligi rivojlanishining prion gipotezasiga, shuningdek, parkinson kasalligining oilaviy va sporadik holatlari genetikasining zamonaviy kontseptsiyalariga alohida e'tibor beriladi [4].

Xulosa: Parkinson kasalligi – asosan neyronlarning degeneratsiyasi bilan bog'liq neyrodegenerativ kasallik bo'lib, uning molekulyar mexanizmlari murakkab va ko'p omilli jarayonlarga asoslangan. Kasallik asosan nigrostrial dopaminergik neyronlarning yo'qolishi va α -sinuklein oqsilining noto'g'ri yig'ilishi bilan bog'liq. Ushbu patologik jarayonlar oksidlovchi stress, mitoxondrial disfunktsiya, proteasoma va autofagiya tizimlarining buzilishi, shuningdek, yallig'lanish va genetik mutatsiyalar bilan bog'liq bo'lishi mumkin. Molekulyar darajada LRRK2, PARKIN, PINK1 va DJ-1 kabi genlar mutatsiyalari kasallik rivojlanishiga sezilarli ta'sir ko'rsatadi. Ayniqsa, mitoxondrial disfunktsiya va oksidlovchi stress neyronlarning apoptotik yo'qolishiga olib keluvchi asosiy omillardan biri hisoblanadi. Shuningdek, α -sinuklein agregatsiyasi Lewy jismlarining shakllanishiga sabab bo'lib, neyronlar faoliyatini buzadi. Shu sababli, Parkinson kasalligiga qarshi terapiyalar molekulyar nishonlarga qaratilgan bo'lib, oksidlovchi stressni kamaytirish, mitoxondrial funktsiyani tiklash, α -sinuklein patologiyasini oldini olish va neyroinflammasiyani bostirishga yo'naltirilgan. Ushbu

mexanizmlarni chuqurroq tushunish yangi dori vositalari va davolash strategiyalarini ishlab chiqishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

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